

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

D 1.3 Open Website Index & Open Crawl Storage Index v1

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
NLNET	Stichting NLnet

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document provides a detailed overview of the first deliverable for D1.3 "Open Website Index & Open Crawl Storage Index", a deliverable of the OpenWebSearch.eu initiative, which is supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme grant agreement number GA 101070014. It outlines the current progress in the development and launch of the Open Website Index & Open Crawl Storage Index. Key features include efficient log aggregation and processing, together with scalable data storage in OpenSearch.

¹ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoudi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*.

v. Document Management

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Michael Granitzer	Coordinator	Approval	29/9/2024

vii. Executive Summary

This report details the development and implementation of the Open Website Index (OWSI) and Open Crawl Storage Index (OCSI) v1 within the OpenWebSearch.eu project. These tools are designed to facilitate large-scale web crawling and data aggregation, providing essential insights for website owners, crawler maintainers, and project administrators. The primary focus is on the aggregation pipeline that processes logs generated by OWLer web crawlers, utilizing Apache Flink and OpenSearch for efficient data processing and storage.

The OpenWebSearch.eu project aims to construct a transparent and inclusive web index. Given the project's scale, managing and analyzing logs from numerous web crawlers presents a significant challenge. The OWSI and OCSI systems were developed to address these challenges by aggregating logs and storing them in a structured format that supports rapid querying and visualization. The aggregation pipeline processes large volumes of log data in real-time, reducing data volume while retaining critical information necessary for operational insights and decision-making.

The main insights generated by aggregating the OWLer crawling activities target the broad spectrum of websites that we have visited along the way. This allows creating a Website Index, which we use to collect interesting information about web hosts and domains. The OWSI data collection forms the backbone of the Open Webmaster Console as a central interaction point for webmasters. We increase transparency by informing the web content owners with detailed statistics on the frequency and extent of our crawling activities. Particularly, the console also enables advanced control mechanisms for webmasters, namely the issuing of take-down request, after seeing that a web page is contained in the Open Web Index.

This report outlines the architecture and implementation of the aggregation pipeline. Apache Flink was selected as the core framework due to its capability to handle large-scale, real-time data processing with fault tolerance and scalability. The pipeline aggregates logs by key entities, such as URLs and domains, allowing for data reduction while preserving important information. The aggregated data is then stored in OpenSearch indices for efficient querying and visualization. The design also considers management of high document counts and ensures system scalability to meet future demands.

The following key results have been achieved:

1. *Efficient Log Aggregation and Processing:* The Apache Flink-based pipeline enables real-time aggregation of logs from OWLer crawlers, reducing log volume by aggregating data based on key entities while retaining important information. This results in reduced data storage requirements and faster query times.
2. *Scalable Data Storage in OpenSearch:* Aggregated data is stored in OpenSearch indices, managed efficiently using best practices such as index rollovers and read-only index configurations. The system can handle high document counts and ensures data availability for querying and analysis.
3. *Optimization:* Optimization efforts have focused on ensuring low latency and high throughput, resulting in a robust and reliable system for real-time operations.
4. *Flexibility for Future Expansion:* The system is designed with scalability in mind, allowing for future expansions and enhancements. This includes potential additions of new data aggregation types, improvements in log input and output speeds, and further simplification of implementation for easier maintenance and updates.

Resources:

- Source: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/log-aggregation>
- Documentation: <https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owler/>

1. Introduction

As the OpenWebSearch.eu project approaches the conclusion of its second year, this report presents an overview of the progress and developments in the Open Website Index (OWSI). It highlights the strategic approach, technical architecture, and operational aspects of the software stack, along with their evolution and ongoing improvements for building an efficient crawling and indexing ecosystem.

1.1 Overview

A cornerstone of the OpenWebSearch.eu project is the implementation of the Open Website Index (OWSI) and Open Crawl Storage Index (OCSI). Both are essential for organizing, aggregating, and making accessible the data collected from numerous web crawlers.

This report examines the details of the OWSI and OCSI, focusing primarily on the aggregation pipeline that processes the logs generated by the OWLer web crawlers. These logs are valuable for understanding the behavior of crawlers and the web pages they visit. Given the large volume of data generated by these crawlers, it is essential to aggregate this information to make it manageable and analyzable. This aggregation not only helps in reducing the data size but also in enhancing the performance of queries, thereby facilitating faster and more efficient data retrieval.

Apache Flink was chosen as the basis for the log processing framework due to its ability to handle large-scale data streams. Flink enables real-time data processing and aggregation, which is essential for the dynamic environment of web crawling. The processed data is stored in OpenSearch, which provides a flexible platform for data indexing and search. This combination of technologies ensures that the data is not only processed efficiently but also stored in a way that maximizes accessibility and usability.

1.2 Vision for the Open Website Index

The OWLer web crawlers, central to the OpenWebSearch.eu project, are responsible for continuously crawling the web, discovering new content, and updating existing information. As these crawlers operate, they generate extensive logs that capture every interaction with web servers, including the URLs crawled, the content fetched, and any errors encountered. However, the large volume of log data generated by multiple crawlers poses significant challenges in terms of storage, processing, and retrieval.

OpenSearch serves as the primary storage and retrieval system for the aggregated log data. Known for its scalability, flexibility, and powerful search capabilities, OpenSearch is widely used for indexing and searching large datasets. In the context of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, these technologies enable fast querying of aggregated data, allowing users to quickly access the information they need, whether it is for monitoring crawler activity, troubleshooting issues, or analyzing web indexing trends.

The project's infrastructure is designed to handle the unique demands of web-scale data processing. The OWLer crawlers are supported by the URL Frontier service, which manages the distribution of URLs to be crawled and handles the results returned by the crawlers. The integration between the crawlers, the URL Frontier service, and the OpenSearch backend ensures a seamless flow of data from log generation to aggregation and analysis.

2. Aggregation Pipeline

2.1 Pipeline Overview

The aggregation pipeline is the core component of the Open Website Index and Open Crawl Storage Index systems, designed to process the substantial volume of logs generated by the OWLer web crawlers. The primary objective of this pipeline is to transform raw crawler log data into meaningful aggregations that facilitate easy querying and analysis. The pipeline architecture is built on Apache Flink, a robust stream processing framework that supports real-time data processing with high fault tolerance and scalability.

Apache Flink is integral to the aggregation pipeline, ingesting logs from OWLer crawlers, processing the data in real-time, and outputting aggregated results. The pipeline consists of a series of data transformation and aggregation steps that filter, transform and group raw log entries into aggregates that provide valuable insights into the crawling activity. Flink's capability to handle both streaming and batch data processing makes it an optimal choice for this task, allowing the system to scale depending on the incoming data load and ensuring efficient processing of large log volumes.

The pipeline ingests logs from a central storage, where they are stored as documents in OpenSearch indices. Flink retrieves these logs, processes them according to predefined rules, and aggregates the data based on key entities such as URLs and domain names. The aggregation process involves grouping log entries with common attributes, such as the same URL or domain, and summarizing the data to retain only the most relevant information. This aggregated data is then stored back in OpenSearch, where users can query it for insights into the crawling activity.

The implementation of this pipeline in Flink enables continuous processing of logs and ensures that, new log entries generated by the crawlers are immediately ingested and processed by the system. This real-time processing capability is essential for maintaining an up-to-date view of crawling activity and ensuring that users can access the latest data without delays. Furthermore, Flink's support for stateful processing and fault tolerance ensures the pipeline's reliability, even under high data loads or in the event of system failures.

2.2 Data Aggregation

The data aggregation process (see Figure 1) focuses on determining which log data should be retained and how it should be grouped. The primary entities for aggregation are URLs and domain names, as these are key points of interest for web administrators and crawler maintainers. Aggregating data at the URL and domain level provides detailed insights into crawling behavior, including which URLs have been crawled, their frequency of access, and the outcomes of these crawls.

Figure 1: Aggregation pipeline.

The aggregation process begins by identifying and extracting relevant fields from each log entry. Important fields include the URL, timestamp, operation type (e.g., crawled, evicted, blacklisted), and crawl-related metadata (e.g., status code, content type). These fields are used to group log entries pertaining to the same URL or domain. The system then applies aggregation functions to summarize the data, such as counting successful and failed crawls, and calculating time intervals between subsequent crawls.

The process also involves decisions about data retention. As storing all raw logs indefinitely is impractical, the pipeline retains only the most essential information for analysis. For example, detailed metadata from individual log entries may be aggregated into summary statistics, while less critical data is discarded to reduce storage requirements. The aim is to balance retaining useful information while minimizing the system's storage and processing load.

A key challenge in data aggregation is managing the variability in log entries. OWLer crawler logs can vary in format and content, depending on the crawl outcome and the specific characteristics of the web server being crawled. The pipeline is designed to be adaptable, using flexible aggregation rules that accommodate different types of log entries. This ensures effective data aggregation across various scenarios, providing a comprehensive overview of crawling activity.

2.3 Data Storage

After aggregation, the data is stored in OpenSearch for subsequent querying and analysis. The storage system is engineered to manage large-scale data efficiently, utilizing best practices for index management and ensuring data accessibility as log volumes increase.

Aggregated data is stored in dedicated indices within OpenSearch, with each index representing a specific time period or data category. This structure facilitates efficient data management, including index rollovers when capacity is reached and the archiving or deletion of older data as necessary. Index management is crucial for system scalability, ensuring that the storage system can accommodate growing log volumes without compromising performance.

A key strategy employed in the system is the use of read-only indices. Once an index is populated with data, it is designated as read-only, preventing further modifications. This approach maintains data consistency and prevents accidental overwrites or corruption. Additionally, read-only indices allow OpenSearch to optimize query performance by focusing on data retrieval without the overhead of write operations.

Managing high document counts presents a significant challenge in the storage system. As log volumes increase, the number of documents stored in OpenSearch indices can become substantial. To address this, the system implements techniques such as index rollovers and sharding, which distribute data across multiple indices and prevent any single index from becoming unmanageable. This distribution method maintains high query performance and ensures users can access aggregated data without significant delays.

3. Implementation Details

3.1 Flink-based Log Processing

The aggregation pipeline implementation utilizes Apache Flink's DataStream API for real-time log processing. The pipeline ingests logs from OWLer crawlers stored in OpenSearch indices, processes them through a series of transformations and aggregations, and produces meaningful data insights.

The pipeline begins with a source component that reads logs from OpenSearch. This source is configured to pull logs in batches, ensuring efficient handling of large data volumes. Once ingested, the logs undergo various transformations to convert raw data into a structured format.

The initial operator is typically a Map function, which transforms each log entry into a structured object, such as a LogEntry class in Java. This transformation normalizes the data and prepares it for further processing.

Subsequently, a Filter operator removes irrelevant or malformed logs that do not meet aggregation criteria. The malformed logs are then recorded for further analysis to see why the aggregation process failed to parse a given URL. This step reduces the load on subsequent pipeline stages by ensuring only valid and meaningful log entries are processed.

A FlatMap operator then splits complex log entries into multiple components if necessary. For example, a log entry containing multiple URLs or actions might be broken down into separate entities for individual processing.

After data normalization and splitting, the aggregation process begins. Logs are grouped by key entities such as URLs or domains using Flink's keyed streams. This allows the pipeline to aggregate all logs related to the same URL or domain, summarizing the data into a single entity.

The aggregation is performed using a windowing function, which groups log entries within a specific time frame. For instance, logs related to a particular URL might be aggregated over a 10-minute window, capturing all activities for that URL within that period.

Finally, the aggregated data is passed to the sink component, which writes the results back to OpenSearch. This ensures persistent storage of the aggregated data, allowing for subsequent user queries. The sink is configured to handle large-scale data storage efficiently, supporting batch writes to optimize performance.

3.2 Handling Concurrency and Fault Tolerance

Concurrency and fault tolerance are essential components of the aggregation pipeline, given the high volume of logs and the requirement for real-time processing. Apache Flink provides robust mechanisms to ensure data consistency and reliability, even under conditions of failure or high load.

Checkpointing is a key feature that enables fault tolerance in Flink. The pipeline is configured to take periodic snapshots of its state, allowing recovery from failures without loss of progress. In the event of a failure, Flink can revert to the last successful checkpoint and resume processing from that point. This ensures that no logs are lost and the pipeline can continue processing without

interruption. The checkpointing mechanism also supports exactly-once processing guarantees, ensuring that each log entry is processed only once, even if the system encounters failures.

In addition to checkpointing, Flink's state management features play a crucial role in maintaining data consistency. The pipeline uses the state to track intermediate results, such as partially aggregated logs. This state is stored in Flink's embedded RocksDB backend, allowing the pipeline to handle large amounts of state data without exceeding memory limits. The state management system ensures that the pipeline can process data efficiently while maintaining the ability to recover from failures.

To manage high ingestion rates of logs, the pipeline incorporates backpressure management. Flink automatically adjusts the data processing rate based on the system's capacity, preventing overloads and ensuring that the pipeline can keep pace with incoming data. This is particularly important when dealing with bursts of log entries, which can occur when multiple crawlers are operating simultaneously. The pipeline's ability to handle backpressure ensures that it remains stable and responsive, even under heavy load.

Logs can sometimes arrive late or in the wrong order, which can lead to incorrect aggregations if not handled properly. These out-of-order log entries present another challenge that the pipeline addresses through event-time processing.

3.3 Integration with OpenSearch

The integration between the Flink-based aggregation pipeline and OpenSearch is a crucial component of the system, facilitating the storage and querying of aggregated data. The pipeline interfaces with OpenSearch using specialized connectors that enable efficient log reading and aggregated data writing.

For writing data to OpenSearch, the pipeline employs bulk indexing to optimize performance by minimizing the number of write operations. This method allows the pipeline to consolidate multiple write operations into a single request, thereby reducing the overhead associated with each write and ensuring the system's capacity to handle large data volumes. This approach is particularly important when managing the high document counts generated by the aggregation process.

Regarding querying, the pipeline utilizes OpenSearch's search APIs to retrieve logs and previous aggregations. Efficient querying is achieved through index management techniques such as index rollovers and sharding.

Example configurations for OpenSearch settings include specifying the number of shards and replicas for each index, as well as configuring index lifecycle management (ILM) policies to automate the rollover and deletion of outdated indices.

4. Statistics of the Open Website Index

Since August 2023, around 10.76B fetches have been conducted in the OWLer crawling pipeline (without complementary crawls, such as Wikipedia, Mastodon, GitLab, etc.). These web page visits are distributed over different 40.5M hosts (Table 1). This is a remarkable number, despite the estimated number of around 193.5M active websites² (a website might comprise several hosts), as the frequency of visits is approximately following a Pareto distribution, with a few platforms getting the most of it.

The vast majority of the conducted fetches were ingested in the Open Website Index. However, we had to take into account a slight deferment of Logs Aggregation. During this interruption, which has ended just recently, we have revised the software and integrated all improvements regarding the first prototype. Overall, OWSI currently comprises around 1.17B web pages in 184 languages.

Visited URLs (per day)³	Up to ~105M / day
Visited URLs (total)	10,757,755,422 until 6 th of August 2024
Unique visited URLs	1,170,925,504 until 6 th of May 2024
Unique visited hosts	40,531,574 until 6 th of May 2024
Number of unique languages	184
Volume of created WARC files	315 TB since October 2023

Table 1: Statistics on General-Purpose crawling (since August 2023)

Top languages

The following table shows the distribution of content languages of all ingested web pages. Compared to Common Crawl's language distribution⁴, we find a bias towards European languages. Our investigations showed that both the crawling location (country of host datacenter) and the HTTP Accept language header impact the distribution of delivered content language diversity.

ISO-639-1	Language Name	Number of Records	Percentage of Records
en	English	1,011,176,753	43.39%
es	Spanish	159,969,683	6.86%
de	German	159,117,969	6.83%
fr	French	144,639,404	6.21%
ru	Russian	111,250,768	4.77%
ja	Japanese	105,304,239	4.52%
zh	Chinese	92,373,956	3.96%
it	Italian	62,906,749	2.70%

² <https://siteefy.com/how-many-websites-are-there/>

³ Note that this number has been achieved during a test crawl spanning 20 days (20.06.2024 - 11.07.2024).

⁴ <https://commoncrawl.github.io/cc-crawl-statistics/plots/languages.html>

nl	Dutch	43,938,946	1.89%
pl	Polish	35,351,504	1.52%
cs	Czech	31,505,202	1.35%
p	Portuguese	29,247,448	1.26%
tr	Turkish	27,696,438	1.19%
vi	Vietnamese	22,060,629	0.95%
in	Indonesian	21,299,915	0.91%
ko	Korean	19,182,754	0.82%
sv	Swedish	18,882,678	0.81%
fa	Persian	16,153,734	0.69%
hu	Hungarian	14,032,688	0.60%
la	Latin	14,022,171	0.60%
ar	Arabic	13,548,963	0.58%
el	Modern Greek (1453-)	13,230,737	0.57%
ro	Romanian	11,775,191	0.51%
fi	Finnish	10,991,315	0.47%
da	Danish	10,049,834	0.43%
sk	Slovak	9,500,760	0.41%
uk	Ukrainian	8,900,802	0.38%
th	Thai	8,729,245	0.37%
no	Norwegian	7,586,160	0.33%
lb	Luxembourgish	7,118,640	0.31%
Other	Other	88,742,312	3.81%

Top domains crawled

The following table shows the top domains crawled in the time between October 2023 and July 2024 to give an overview on the domain distribution in our crawl. This domain distribution in the crawl is further reflected in the Open Website Index.

Domain	Fraction	Absolute Count
blogspot.com	0,2354%	5,563,708
wordpress.com	0,1078%	2,549,134
wikipedia.org	0,0849%	2,007,679
fc2.com	0,0380%	897,966
hatenablog.com	0,0295%	696,717
europa.eu	0,0238%	561,532
free.fr	0,0228%	539,715
yahoo.com	0,0218%	516,114
web.app	0,0158%	374,451
altervista.org	0,0119%	280,728
medium.com	0,0116%	273,705
nih.gov	0,0104%	246,284
amazonaws.com	0,0101%	238,429
google.com	0,0092%	218,500
netlify.app	0,0084%	198,200
mit.edu	0,0077%	183,035
cloudfront.net	0,0072%	170,450
harvard.edu	0,0072%	169,597
cocolog-nifty.com	0,0067%	158,705
stackexchange.com	0,0064%	150,372

uk.com	0,0063%	148,608
spb.ru	0,0061%	143,962
sakura.ne.jp	0,0059%	138,732
wikidot.com	0,0056%	131,904
nasa.gov	0,0053%	125,834
mpg.de	0,0051%	121,058
appspot.com	0,0051%	119,594
microsoft.com	0,0049%	115,341
us.com	0,0049%	114,770
etc.	-	-

5. Data format

5.1 Current Aggregated Data Structure

The following list outlines the information collated for single URLs. This information is a subset of the details collected during crawling and is further aggregated by the presented Apache Flink Job. It includes both basic information, such as the URL, the public suffix, and the timestamp of the first and last recorded visit, as well as technical details, such as number of failed fetches. Furthermore, we record certain metadata flags, which we initially considered interesting for further analysis. These include for example “isPrivacyPolicy” as well as the so-called “web page category” (based on a hierarchical schema to classify web content similar to Curlie⁵). Some listed details, such as the recorded ratios, or the recorded reason for an internal MalformedURLException (“malformedReason”) are tracked to facilitate future debugging.

firstSeen (date)	ratios:
lastSeen (date)	- evictionToCrawl (float)
url (str)	- evictionToFailedCrawl (float)
blacklist:	- evictionToSuccessfulCrawl (float)
- firstBlacklisted (date)	- successfulCrawlToFailedCrawl (float)
- lastBlacklisted (date)	timeBetweenCrawls:
counter:	- all:
- crawlFailures (long)	- earliestEntry (date)
- crawlSuccesses (long)	- lastEntry (date)
- crawls (long)	- max (long)
- evictions (long)	- min (long)
info:	- failed:
- host (str)	- earliestEntry (date)
- publicSuffix (str)	- lastEntry (date)
- reverseDomain (str)	- max (long)
- pathLen (long)	- min (long)
- discoveryDepth (long)	- success:
- malformedReason (str)	- earliestEntry (date)
- discoveryDate (date)	- lastEntry (date)
- isSitemap (boolean)	- max (long)
- isAdult (boolean)	- min (long)
- isPrivacyPolicy (boolean)	timeBetweenEvictions:
- category (str)	- earliestEntry (date)
- categoryProbability (float)	- lastEntry (date)
- language (str)	- max (long)
	- min (long)

⁵ <https://curlie.org/>

The Flink Job further aggregates the collected information for each URL on the level of hosts (e.g., www.ows.eu). The recorded information collated on the host level is further enriched with details regarding the document types that have been found on the respective website. Metadata flags like “isAdult” are aggregated by counting the number of recorded *true* and *false* values, as well as tracking the most recently recorded value.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> firstSeen (date) lastSeen (date) domain (str) blacklist: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - firstBlacklisted (date) - lastBlacklisted (date) content: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - isAdult: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lastValue (boolean) - countTrue (integer) - countFalse (integer) - flagTrue: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long) - flagFalse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long) - isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) - hasHtml:- isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) - hasImage:- isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) - hasXML:- isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) - hasJSON:- isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) - hasBinary:- isMalicious: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (schema identical to is Adult) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> counter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - crawlFailures (long) - crawlSuccesses (long) - crawls (long) - evictions (long) info: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reverseDomain (str) - domainLen (integer) - malformedReason (str) ratios: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evictionToCrawl (float) - evictionToFailedCrawl (float) - evictionToSuccessfulCrawl (float) - successfulCrawlToFailedCrawl (float) timeBetweenCrawls: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - all: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long) - failed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long) - success: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long) timeBetweenEvictions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - earliestEntry (date) - lastEntry (date) - max (long) - min (long)
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5.2 Prospective Aggregated Data Structure

After the first phase of running the Logs Aggregation Pipeline and collecting data, we have prototyped the public dashboard, which makes the Open Website Index accessible to users. During this prototyping process and in exchange with our third-party project partners, we could refine our comprehension of what information is most useful. Consequently, we have adapted the aggregated data structures on URLs and host level. Major part of our work on OWSI in the recent months was to integrate these new improvements and learnings into the initial version of the Logs Aggregation pipeline. This effort is about to be finished and be reported in the next Deliverable on the Open Website Index.

The following lists outline the refined aggregated data structures on URL and host level. Note that some fields are renamed for clearer nomination, e.g. “firstVisited” and “lastVisited” (instead of “firstSeen” and “lastSeen”). On both levels, the elements of the object “fetch.statusCode” (200, 301, etc.) are counters, counting the number of occurrences of the respective status codes on the corresponding web page or website. Tags is a list of encountered metadata tags created by OWLer during the crawling process. “DiscoveredThrough” is the so-called referrer URL.

URL level:	Host level:
url (str)	pld (str)
pld (str)	host (str)
host (str)	firstVisited (date)
firstVisited (date)	lastVisited (date)
lastVisited (date)	countFetches (long)
countFetches (long)	countErrors (long)
countErrors (long)	lastError (str)
lastError (str)	urls (list of str)
fetchInterval:	tags (list of str)
- min (long)	fetch.statusCode:
- max (long)	- 200 (long)
- sum (long)	- 301 (long)
- avg (long)	- etc.
discoveredThrough (str)	
tags (list of str)	
fetch.statusCode:	
- 200 (long)	
- 301 (long)	
- etc.	

6. Conclusion and Outlook

This report has detailed how the aggregation pipeline, utilizing Apache Flink and integrated with OpenSearch, processes extensive log data generated by web crawlers. The pipeline effectively reduces raw data volume into meaningful aggregations, facilitating easier storage, querying, and analysis. The implementation of OpenSearch as the primary data storage solution ensures system scalability and the capacity to manage large data volumes inherent in web indexing projects.

Future developments could focus on enhancing the capabilities of the aggregation pipeline, allowing for more rapid data processing and immediate insights. Additionally, we want to revise the current processing pipeline and integrate more insightful information in the Open Website Index.

7. Appendix

7.1 Open Website Index (OWSI)

We have incorporated a dedicated website to share the details and the insights of our crawling efforts. It also offers the possibility to download our curated datasets and monitor our daily crawls.

Webpage: <https://dashboard.ows.eu>

7.2 List of Acronyms

Acronym or Abbreviation	Term
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung
CFT	Crawler Frontier Tier
CIFF	Common Index File Format
CCT	Crawling Cluster Tier
DEM	Demonstrator
DG Connect	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
ECJ	European Court of Justice/ D6.1, page 29, European Court of Justice (EuGH), need to be double checked!
DSM	Digital Single Market
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
ELSA	Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects
EULA	End User License Agreement
FSTP	Financial Support to Third-parties
GPU	Graphics Processor Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HORISON-RIA	Horison - Research and Innovation Action
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IPR Management	Intellectual Property Management

IST	Index and Storage Tier
LLMs	Large Language Models
LTD	Limited (Liability company)
MEP	Member of European Parliament
MP	Member of a Parliament
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWSI	Open Website Index
OWLer	Open Web Search Crawler
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
OWSAI	Open Web Search and Analysis Infrastructure
PCT	Project Core Team
PET	Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier
PPET	Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier
RIA	Research and Innovations Action
SERPs	Search Engine Results Pages
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
OWC	Open Webmaster Console
VM	Virtual Machine
WARC / warc /Warc	Web Archive Fileformat